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JAPANESE "KAIZEN" CONCEPT AS A PRACTICE TO IMPROVE THE ACTIVITIES OF MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS IN REFORMING CONDITIONS

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O. Hromtseva, V. Striukov. Japanese "Kaizen" concept as a practice to improve the activities of medical institutions in reforming conditions. The paper defines the essence of the Kaizen philosophy and its value in modern transformational conditions. There was substantiated the expediency of the Kaizen concept in order to improve the activity of medical institutions during the medical reform. The main elements and principles of this concept are considered and their characteristics are given. The specific activity features of the health care institutions, which should be taken into account when using the Kaizen concept, are analyzed. The necessity of forming a corporate culture in conditions without interruption of the organization's activity is proved. The description of the main Kaizen-tools, which is expediently used during the activities improvement of medical institutions, is given. The main stages of Kaizen system implementation in the medical institution are presented.

Keywords: medical reform, medical institution, Kaizen concept, corporate culture, continuous improvement of activities, quality management

Medical reform in Ukraine is aimed at modernizing healthcare facilities, moving to up-to-date standards for the provision of medical services. The reform process must change both the culture of medical institutions and organizational changes in general. At the same time, it is necessary, first of all, to pay attention to the competence of the heads of health care institutions, the principles, and methods by which the management and personnel work is performed.

Medical management involves managing financial, labor and material resources of health facilities. The main goal of healthcare management is to reduce the losses of Ukrainian society from morbidity, disability, and mortality. In the context of the economic crisis, the need to improve the efficiency of health facilities is of particular importance, which requires the introduction of new forms, methods, and models of management of all units of the medical institution as a system.

In modern transformation, it is necessary to pay attention to such aspects as conducting socially responsible business, development of a high corporate culture of the organization, establishment of long-term relationships with customers, development of a special approach to consumers of medical services, ensuring the competitiveness of the organization. To achieve these objectives, various standards are developed that take into account the specific features of a particular institution, personnel training is carried out, methods of organization and optimization of the work process are implemented. All this is due to the introduction of a quality management system. Most institutions recognize that the quality of products or services is an integral part of a successful organization. It should be noted that all these processes in the medical sector proceed much slower. At the same time, there is already a successful experience in introducing both the quality management system and other modern management technologies and concepts in medicine.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

The importance of application and Kaizen's management principles in the enterprise management system is vividly debated by many Ukrainian and foreign scientists, embodied in the papers of such researchers as Imai(1986), Jacobson et al.(2009), Colenso (2000), Deming (2012), et al.

But it should be noted that despite a fairly large number of publications by scholars on the application of the Kaizen concept at enterprises, the study and practical application of Kaizen management in local health care institutions remains inadequately developed and studied.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Quality management systems do not prevent mistakes in a medical facility and do not help to respond quickly to changes in the environment. Only in combination with an effective system for improving processes that is capable of rapid modification, it is possible to use the great potential that provides the medical organization with a quality management system.

This approach to management offers the Kaizen concept of Japanese philosophy or practice, which focuses on the continuous improvement of the processes of production, development, auxiliary business processes, and management, as well as all aspects of life. In simple words, this is a constant improvement. This concept has long ago found its application among Japanese managers and is gradually being implemented worldwide.

The aim of the article is to study the features of the Kaizen concept and to substantiate the feasibility of using its tools and methods in healthcare institutions in order to improve their activities in the context of medical sector reform.

The main part

One of the most interesting events of the last decade was the introduction of the Kaizen concept in healthcare facilities. Today, demographic and economic conditions are such that many hospitals need to serve more patients without relying on additional funding or staff increase.

Kaizen is one of the approaches to improving the organization's work. This term appeared in Japan and began to denote a system of interrelated actions that lead to an increase in the quality of products, processes and management systems. In the modern sense, Kaizen is a system of continuous improvement of quality, technologies, processes, corporate culture, productivity, reliability, leadership and other aspects of the company's operations.

Kaizen system mainly focuses on the personnel "quality", because the quality of products and services depends exactly on the personnel. This system involves the process of improving each employee - from the head of the highest level to an ordinary employee (Chulanova, & Glyuta, 2014).

Each organization employee offers small improvements on a regular basis. Suggestions are made not occasionally during a month or a year, but constantly. In the major, there are not global, yet minor improvements. This is the essence of the Kaizen system – a large number of small, minor improvements lead to a significant improvement in quality.

The suggestions for improvement that employees present may not be limited to a particular area, such as production or marketing. Kaizen is based on making changes wherever improvements can be made.

At the beginning of the Korean War, Toyota was in a similar situation: the demand for trucks began to increase, but banks did not allow the company to hire new people due to financial problems. There was used Kaizen instead of money; the result is well-known.

The healthcare sector has a distinctive feature: the flow of the value creation is built around the consumer, who in most cases is a patient. At the start of the system, there is a person who complains about this or that malaise. In the end, instead of the finished product, there is the person who was assisted to get recovered (Liker, 2004).

The Kaizen system key features are 5 key elements. In order it can work properly and to become an effective tool for improving the quality, the organization must create the conditions for their implementation.

The first element is a teamwork. All employees should work as one team to achieve a common goal and desired improvement in work. Employees of all levels must do everything possible for the benefit of their colleagues and the company. Work in the team involves constant information exchange, mutual learning, timely performance of their duties, and so on.

The second element is personal discipline. Discipline is paramount to success. Kaizen calls for each employee to increase own self-discipline in all aspects of work - managing own time, the work quality, compliance with requirements and regulations, using material and financial resources, etc.

The third element is the moral state. Regardless of whether the company succeeds in implementing changes or not, the personnel should strive to maintain a high moral standard. The top management should introduce into practice a variety of motivational tools such as comfortable working conditions, a system of incentives and rewards, paid leave, benefits, medical services, loans to employees, etc.

The fourth element is the quality circles. This is one of the most important elements of the Kaizen system. The organization needs to arrange quality circles work. The groups of these circles should include employees of different levels. In quality circles, employees have the opportunity to share ideas, skills, technologies and other resources that are important for collaboration. The exchange of information and interaction within the framework of quality circles allows employees to evaluate the effectiveness of their work on the basis of comparison with the work of others, and thus try to improve their activities.

The fifth element is the improvement suggestions. It is necessary to give employees the opportunity to freely suggest improvements regardless of the rank held in the management system. The employees' suggestions can be of any type, even absurd, and they all have to be considered and considered (Colenso, 2000).

According to Masaaki Imai, the Kaizen is a whole philosophy, a worldview that should become a way of life for every employee. Unlike the quality management system, this is a comprehensive system that covers several subsystems such as 5S, JIT, Quality Circles, TPM, Kanban, and many others.

Moreover, the Kaizen gives space for thoughts and ideas on how to improve processes, enabling the development of a unique model adapted to the peculiarities of the organization and covering all spheres of its activities, while the quality management system only regulates processes that are clearly certified and spelled out in standards. In order to raise the existing

standards of activity to a higher level, it is necessary to continuously improve the current processes. That is why the implementation of the Kaizen concept in medical organizations becomes relevant (Masaaki, 2005).

The implementation of the Kaizen system in practice implies adherence to the basic principles of this system:

- the workplace organization;
- unjustified losses elimination;
- standardization.

1. The workplace organization is the workplace management in order to optimize the activities. And the Kaizen system pays great attention to this issue. In the Japanese version, this process is denoted by the "gemba" term. Appropriate management tools, called the 5S methodology, are used to properly organize the workplace. The very 5S term comes from the first letters of the Japanese words.

Fig. 1. 5S-Methodology

Source: Compiled by authors based on the papers (Masaaki, 2012)

Seiri – one needs to sort out the things that are not needed in the work. Special markings may be used to allocate unwanted items. If the elements marked with marking are not demanded by anyone while performing work, then they are removed from the workplace.

Seiton – one needs to put everything in order. These elements should be in sight. Tools and devices should be located in places where they can easily be detected.

Seiso – the workplace and all equipment must be clean. At the end of each working day, the workplace must be cleaned, and all tools and equipment get placed in the places.

Seiketsu – standardization of the first three steps. These actions should become a common practice. When employees of the organization see improvement from the proper workplace organization, it is necessary to conduct training with them on the actions implementation.

Shitsuke – maintaining a sustainable workplace management practice. It is necessary to create a system for monitoring the content of the organized and standardized workplaces.

2. Removing unjustified losses is a process of finding and eliminating actions in processes that do not add the value. In the Japanese version, this process is called "muda". Most works are a sequence of actions that convert the source material into a finished product. Some of these actions add value to the product, and part does not. The part that does not add the value is a loss and should be eliminated.

3. Standardization is a process of standardizing work. Standardization creates the basis for stable work, but standards must be changed when changing both the external and internal environment. In the Kaizen system, the standardization process never ends. Standards are constantly being refined. Standard improvements are performed in the PDCA cycle.

The PDCA cycle is a well-known continuous process improvement model known as the Shuhart-Deming cycle or the PDCA- P for the plan, D for do, C for check, A for act, when applied in a wide variety of applications, allows to effectively managing this activity on a system basis (Deming, 2012).

When implementing the Kaizen concept in medical institutions, it is necessary to take into account a number of nuances.

Since the Kaizen concept works with human resistance to the changes, the first step is to mentally prepare the employees for the Kaizen tools before the implementation process begins. It is necessary to introduce each employee into the course of the case in order to maximize the effect of the concept being implemented. As a preliminary step, time should be given for discussing philosophy and its benefits.

The next step in the implementation of the concept is to eliminate internal barriers for employees. In fact, one of the fundamental aspects of the Kaizen system is the relationship between colleagues. The medical organization success, achievement of the common goal depends on the effective and successful interaction of the employees. However, most often in organizations with a linearly functional organizational structure, there is a problem of interaction not only between employees but also between divisions. Moreover, when conducting internal audits in organizations that implemented a quality management system, it was found that one of the main reasons for non-compliance with corrective actions is the lack of clear interaction between departments. It is worth noting that in medical organizations, employees should be considered as internal consumers within the corporate culture.

Every employee of the treatment and care institution must remember that patients and other visitors evaluate the health facility as a whole, but feel the atmosphere of the institution in details. If each staff member of a medical institution adheres to the internal culture of behavior, the rules of medical ethics, understand own responsibility, then in case of work disruptions of the whole team reduced to a minimum (Petrovskiy, 2008).

It should be borne in mind that the organizational culture of a health facility includes a professional security culture. Under the security culture it is necessary to understand the system of values, goals, knowledge, and skills, the rules of procedures, beliefs shared by the representatives of a certain medical profession (doctors of a certain specialization, middle and junior personnel, administration, etc.), support patients, create a favorable working climate, an atmosphere of trust and become an effective tool for achieving the goal of the organization (Hromtseva, & Krupskiy, 2016).

Formation and implementation of corporate culture is a complicated matter. But the stronger the corporate culture, the better the reputation of the medical institution. That is, the corporate culture directly correlates with the trust of patients and the welfare of a medical institution. Every head of a medical establishment understands that satisfaction of patients and visitors of a medical institution, their reluctance to return and become regular clients largely depends not only on the professionalism of the doctor and his assistants, but also the overall impression of coherence in the work of all employees of the medical institution and the visible side of the interpersonal relationships in the team. After all, in modern society, informative flows point to the need for awareness of the importance of prophylactic medicine as a way of preventing health disorders. Therefore, the heads of medical institutions pay attention to the formation of a corporate culture and monitoring the fulfillment of requirements (Uglov, 2007).

In this case, particular attention is paid to the human resources management of the medical organization. In case of inappropriate use of qualification and other abilities of employees, even if the medical institution has a perfect material and technical base of production, has the latest equipment and technology, the production process cannot be carried out normally and the use of the Kaizen concept does not make any sense.

But each employee, in turn, must clearly understand who is the internal consumer, that is, whom he interacts with, how own work relates to the work of other people, the means of communication between colleagues, and so on. In order for each employee to have a coherent picture of the interaction with their colleagues, it is proposed to implement such a Kaizen tool as a communication card. It shows the connections between employees in the organization, as well as channels of working communication.

The third step in implementing the Kaizen principles is to create quality control circles and develop a supply system (fig. 2).

For example, the system of suggestions submission for improvement can take place, training is held ("Principles of total quality management", "Formation of a corporate culture oriented to quality", etc.). Quarterly on the management level there should be considered the results and opportunities for introducing suggestions. However, the Kaizen culture means the involvement of all organization's personnel in improving processes. To implement the strategy, it is advisable to create the Kaizen groups (circles) in each department, since only employees who work in a particular subdivision will be able to offer effective ways to improve own work processes. The main task of the groups is to resolve private issues related to quality within the policy and objectives in terms of the quality of the medical organization.

For the more effective functioning of the Kaizen groups, weekly meetings are required to discuss the following issues:

- the current state of affairs in the subdivision (report);
- detected during internal audits of non-compliance (in the presence of a quality management system);
- goals and tasks for improvement of work processes;
- which Kaizen tools will be used;
- a concrete action plan.

The Kaizen group also has a system for suggestions submission.

To develop a more structured system it is proposed to divide the process of submitting suggestions to the stages, at each of which the suggestion will be processed before bringing to leadership (McAlearney, et. al, 2013).

An employee, who has an idea to improve any aspect of their activities or the entire medical organization, is invited to first report on the idea to the Kaizen group, which operates in the unit. The group, in turn, evaluates the idea, conducts

brainstorming, identifies the potential benefits of implementing the idea. Moreover, the employee who proposed the idea actively participates in further analysis and also heads the business project (if the idea is accepted later on). Thus, the Kaizen group develops a suggestion that includes a cost-benefit analysis and clearly shows how the idea can increase the level of consumer satisfaction, which is the main indicator of the value of the proposed improvement measure.

Fig. 2. Organizational system of the suggestions submission
 Source: Compiled by the author based on the papers (Falovich, 2013)

Once the suggestion has been developed, it should be shown to the Kaizen group leader, and then to the other groups' leaders, whose activities will be influenced by the idea implementation. Then the group leader should show the fully worked out suggestion to the head of the unit, and he/she, in turn, decides on the suggestion whether it makes sense to bring that to the chief doctor and ask for the funds' allocation for testing the idea. If approved, the arrangement of the testing followed by the full-scale implementation with successful testing will entirely lie on the Kaizen group where the idea was born. When approving a suggestion, it is important to be guided by the question of whether the idea will improve standards of work quality.

Only an idea that lets one achieve, for example, higher speeds, lower costs, can be considered worthy of implementation.

After the project realization, one should not forget about the remuneration of the employee who submitted the idea and the whole group for implementation. The reward may be monetary or moral in the form of awards and other signs of honor, and this may also be a promotion based on the scale of the project and the benefits received. However, one should not forget about employees whose ideas have not succeeded and have not been implemented. Such personnel should also be encouraged so as not to lose the incentive for further improvement. Moreover, it is recommended that unrealized suggestions be returned with the comments to the creator and thankfulness for the efforts made to improve the processes.

This suggestions submission system maximizes teamwork, which is one of the key points of the Kaizen concept. The number of suggestions from a particular group can be judged by the desire of employees to improve the functioning of the medical organization and the level of competence of employees who can find opportunities to even improve in its functional unit.

This information on this system can serve as a further basis and an additional criterion in the system of analysis by management.

According to the Kaizen concept, all improvements begin with the workplace (gemba), and in order to identify the problem, first of all one needs to go right there. For greater productivity, the workplace of any employee should be in perfect order and maximally adapted for effective work. It is suggested to introduce such a tool as a threat notification. These messages are more focused on the work of nurses and middle personnel who make mistakes when performing one or another procedure. However, in the future, such a tool will serve as an effective way to analyze and develop corrective actions for own errors. These threat reports are submitted to the Kaizen group, and then they are analyzed and submitted to the Unit Manager in the form of monthly reports (Liker, 2004).

And finally, the last step in implementing the Kaizen principles in a medical organization is the Kaizen-blitz, which should launch the Kaizen tool implementation, and will help to identify, in a few days, the reasons that cause ineffective work and generate specific performance enhancements. The objectives of this case are learning and gaining the experience of quick Kaizen transformations, as well as a vivid proof of the effectiveness of these tools (Mazzocato et al., 2010).

Daily plan in the Kaizen-blitz can be presented in the following format (fig. 3).

Fig.3. Planning in the Kaizen-Blitz format

Source: Compiled by authors based on the papers (Laraia et al., 1999)

Such Kaizen-blitz is a kind of educational project that within four days shows the real use of some of the elements of the suggested Kaizen tools and proves the efficiency and value of the Japanese concept.

Conclusions

Kaizen is a technological approach when the management of the company and its employees are continuously improving.

Kaizen Principles in Medical Institutions:

- concentration on patients (medical organizations should be in line with the patient's choice; personal responsibility of the personnel is also required);
- continuous changes with small steps (each improvement of any processes is implemented as a new formal standard);
- open recognition and identification of problems (making them publicly discussed);
- openness principle promotion;
- creation of working teams (Kaizen groups) and network structures;
- management of various projects with the help of functional commands;
- formation of self-discipline (respect for oneself and organization);
- informing each employee;
- the delegation of authority to each employee.

As the world experience and trends in the development of modern organizations show, the Japanese management system has proven its uniqueness and efficiency through specific strategies and tools. The considered Kaizen concept demonstrates the great value gained from the Kaizen tools when improving the organization. These approaches can be applied quite effectively in the activities of medical organizations, and this issue requires its further development, taking into account the specifics of activities in the healthcare.

In conclusion, it can be noted that while conducting the Kaizen concept, the medical institutions can improve the availability and quality of medical care. The above methods application allows quick solving emerging problems, prevent their appearance, and sometimes outstrip consumers' demands, thereby responding quickly to any innovations.

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